

Prospects of Business to Business Marketing in Pakistan: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 07, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords</p> <p>Online marketing; Business to Business Marketing, Demographical Characteristics; Personal Experiences; Technology Usage</p>	<p><i>Online media usage for marketing and commercial purposes is trending today. Business organizations mostly prefer online platforms to access international markets worldwide. The current study also aims to highlight the importance of online marketing in the Business to Business marketing context. The researcher used a cross-sectional study design and selected a sample of n=, 225 respondents, from three main cities of Pakistan. The current study is also supported by Channel Expansion Theory that further validates the notion of online media usage for marketing purposes. Data gathered from the quantitative survey revealed that customers perceive online marketing as an essential part of expanding their Business. Here the role of personal characteristics, previous experiences and upgrading the technology by advertising agencies is of greater magnitude. Thus, the researcher concluded that online marketing in general and online Business to Business marketing in particular, have brighter prospects in Pakistan. If advertising agencies focus more on upgrading their strategies through online platforms' usage, international manufacturers will prefer Pakistan as a highly profitable arena.</i></p>
<p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4495290</p>	

Introduction

When a new business organization starts working, or an existing organization aims to accomplish sustainability, the primary objective is to generate revenue and avail progression. For this purpose, commercial organizations design effective policies and utilize strategies to promote their products or services and resort to advertising. As advertising is the process based on the execution and implementation of plans, distributing goods, services, and achieving individuals and collective objectives are the primary business goals (Kutler, 2003). In this regard, marketing is a fundamental aspect to meet the organizational goals because it is a strategy that can help the organization to expand and progress (Constantinides, 2014). Advertising helps to communicate with customers and share the details regarding products and services. Today advertising is a key to designing general marketing due to its universality, visibility and accessibility that make it a vital subject globally.

Moreover, advertising does not constitute a simple process. Instead, it contains several social, psychological and economic approaches that multi-directional and planned accordingly (Economic, 2013). Likewise, the methods, techniques, strategies and types of advertising extensively modified over time. Several studies witnessed substantial changes and improvements in advertising content, resulting in better business outcomes (Batra & Keller, 2016). For instance, the emergence of internet advertising highly improved marketing strategies. As it is one of the most effective means of communication, it widely facilitated advertising and marketing (Kent, Brink & Bridge, 2006). As noted by Jolly, A., Skiles, B., Cousins, L., Grobbel, W., Sandoz, A., Williams, (2020), online marketing is a mixture of new advertising approaches and improved marketing strategies. Here the aims are to expanding the efforts, spending energy in comparatively more competitive arenas, and utilizing the existing assets to search for better revenue generating opportunities (Jober & Fahi,

2009). The potential of online marketing can be seen when more than 85% of social media users in Europe shopped online in 2012, which provided more great opportunities to use and develop the online marketing (IAB Europe, 2012). With the recent global Internet usage of approximately three billion people and a historical annual growth average of 20 percent in the last 12 years (Internet World Stats, 2015), the number of online consumers will be kept on increasing. As today, more people are now relying on social media, it is not surprising that consumers, sellers and marketers prefer Internet (Datta et al., 2018).

Furthermore, Web advertising utilizes the Internet to distribute marketing messages to a massive number of audience. The adoption and integration of the Internet in advertisement transformed the advertising techniques and approaches (Alghizzawi et al., 2019). Today, the online Business to business marketing advertising is a modified and developed way of sustainable customer loyalty, and availing the business goals. New media technology revolutionized marketing arenas. Today, marketers are adopting strategic approaches to access their audience and persuade them more effectively. (Habes et al., 2020). Particularly in Pakistan, the adopting and integration of new media technology for Business to business marketing purposes is a distinguished initiative. As from the business perspective, social media provides a direct exposure to the product/services, enables two-way communication, and help to fulfil the clients' demands (Amjad, 2015). Therefore, the evolution of online advertising's can improve advertiser-consumers' relationships and build positive perceptions about the product and the services. The briskly emerging can also bridge the communication gaps between clients and service providers (Hill, 2007).

Therefore, by keeping in view the changing role of media due to technological advancement, business organizations should adopt new techniques as primitive advertising approaches to meet their organizational goals (Presbry, 2009). Thus, the current study also aims to analyze the factors affecting clients' opinion about online Business to business marketing advertising, impacts of marketing services and the impacts of integrating online Business to business marketing. As noted by (Ohajionu & Mathews, 2015a), due to ease of accessibility and direct communication, online media offers brighter prospects to business organizations. Especially for the Business to business marketing, the access is more reliable and fruitful both for the sellers and the potential customers. The researcher investigated the three main research questions:

Literature Review:

Business to Business Marketing:

Previous studies explicitly differentiate between Business to Business (B2B) and Business to Client (B2C) marketing. However, after more than forty years, contemporary critics and researchers questioned whether there had been no common ground for consumers and industrial marketing in the past (Khokar, 2016). Phil & Arrow (2015) differentiated Business to Business marketing and individual consumer marketing in terms of their exchange of products and types of customers. Based on these crucial differences, market researchers emphasize on developing a particular marketing technique for each market (Presbry, 2009).

In Business to Business marketing, the relationship between consumers and the seller is unique yet complex as it is based on "transaction exchange" and "collaborative exchange" (Toding, 2017). In Business to Business marketing, this relationship is complicated as it is based on industrial purchases instead of individual usage, including other various actors, i.e. members of the decision-making department (Bandgar, 2014). Gilliland & Johnston, (2017) further highlighted the activities and purposes of Business to Business marketing to attract and convince bidders, stakeholders, buyers and suppliers. These activities have a strong influence on the decision-making process and demand for tactful strategies for persuasion.

Here Alghizzawi et al., (2019) emphasized that consumers should have direct accessibility and exposure to products which can remove their uncertainties. For example, in the high tech markets, consumers have greater exposure to products and services, and they are particular about the product quality and services. Moreover, in the high tech markets, the customer-seller relationship is of greater importance due to increased competition and standards of commitment (Ali et al., 2019). In this regard, high tech markets pay particular consideration to maintain robust customer-organization relationship to sustain the products and services providing process (Ohajionu & Mathews, 2015a).

Business to Business Marketing and Internet Advertising:

Business to Business marketing plays an essential role in economic improvement through online platforms. In the upcoming years, technological advancements will also accelerate the revenue-generating process through advanced online marketing strategies (Matthyssens et al., 2008). Business to Business marketing will demand more strategic approaches and design, Strategies and tactics associated with the revolution are driven by B2B marketing, enabling both sellers and customers to earn and retain more significant revenue. These changes will transform all business functions and create an entirely new trend in business arenas (Papadopoulos, 2009). Competitiveness is the only factor that accelerated Business to Business marketing to compete Business to Client and added other essential features such as innovation and economic transformation. However, in the Business to Client Marketing, the reason to utilize the web largely relies on changes in consumer preferences and the benefactions offered by new technologies (Hameed, 2014). But in the Business to Business marketing, web technology usage primarily depends upon and marketing requirements. As the organization believes in leveraging web technology to improve its business function, customers, and suppliers record (Akber et al., 2013).

Indeed, initiatives such as Electronic Data Interchange and on-time delivery have improved the customer-seller relationships in Business to Business marketing arenas. These improved relationships also led to specific significant changes, such as implementing logistics and construction activities. Moreover, due to web-based technologies, new models and approaches of marketing have significantly reshaped the conventional Business to Business marketing (Grundmeyer, 2012). Undoubtedly, online transactions are also playing a prominent role in facilitating buyers and sellers in Business to Business transactions. However, Business to Business marketing also involves complex patterns of communication between sellers and buyers (Pishva, 2013). The excessive focus on transactional-focused exchanges also neglects the risks and more opportunities that web-based Business to Business marketers offer. These Customer Relationship Management based advertising plans enable business organizations to acquire new customers (Carlson & Zmud, 1994). Therefore, the improved and better strategies associated with Business to Business marketing aims to transform all the business operations. It significantly changed innovations with comprehensive production processes, replaceable parts, and assembly lines (Berman, 2017).

Online Advertisement in Pakistan

Online advertising is accessible with fast and 24 hours' services. Unlike traditional media advertisements, online advertisements are available without any limitations. For this reason, online advertisements are among the most preferred, resulting in fruitful outcomes (Wadhawan, 2016). Moreover, increasing social networking sites are also facilitating the advertising process as multiple platforms reach a massive number of audience worldwide. Today, there are hundreds of online platforms for news, entertainment, information and communication. Users switch from one side to the other in search of their desired content which also provides them with exposure to the online advertisements (Ibrahim, 2012).

Similarly, in Pakistan, online advertisements are trending due to the feasibility, cost-effectiveness and accessibility. Even advertising agencies also adopt different tactics to attract the audience attention and convince them to consider further the products and services (Talha, 2011) as internet advertising in Pakistan is following international trends and innovations. To cope with the changing business challenges, technology, and patterns of cultural and ethical adaptation. However, a few years ago, there were very few online platforms to market in Pakistan, and all the advertisement was relying on traditional media marketing patterns (Hadadi & Almsafir, 2013).

With the rise of internet usage, the popularity of online advertising also increased in Pakistan (Nizam et al., 2018). Initially, a minimal number of local companies began taking benefit of the available online platforms to market their products (Rahman et al., 2018). The popularity of online marketing increased with the growth of new yet small business organizations. New organizations forced the online platforms transforming to become more vigilant and strategic to obtain a competitive advantage and become a transforming aspect of the advertising landscape in Pakistan (Haider & Shakib, 2018). Due to increased business investments, several foreign companies also started considering Pakistan as an essential market place and started resorting to online marketing in Pakistan (Ahmed et al., 2019).

Theoretical Framework:

Channel Expansion Theory provides strong conceptual support to the current study. As noted by Germonprez, (2002), choosing the desired platform to communicate, availing information, and entertainment relies upon our opinion regarding the medium. Today social media is the most source of information, and we have readily adopted it. Further validated by Rains, (2008) as he considers the Channel Expansion Theory as generalizable on both new and traditional media types. According to Deursen & Pieterse, (2000), the advancement and integration of the Internet as a transformation of traditional media into new media also addressed people's concerns about the role and usability of the Internet. However, initially, Channel Expansion Theory received very little attention from the researchers. Focusing on the Channel Expansion Theory (Zimmerman & Blythe, 2013) investigated communication in the organization and respondents' views. The researcher only assessed E-mail as a source of communication to provide a new direction to the Channel Expansion Theory. Moreover, Yang et al., (2011) also found a strong significant relationship between perceived self-efficacy among online media users' and their positive opinions for the Internet as a comparatively more effective resource of communication, information and knowledge.

Likewise, commercial organizations also make special considerations for online media for marketing purposes. Due to increased communication, direct access to consumers and convince them to make favourable decisions is of more significant concern (Duffy, 2005). Today, online platforms help marketers to increase the observability of their products/goods and access the customers (Israel & Wilson, 2006). Ishii et al., (2019) further highlighted the significance of advertising agencies to make strategies to use online platforms as a quick way of communication. Despite much criticism by the researchers, policymakers and stakeholders new media greatly facilitates the commercial interest as both customers and the marketers take advantage of fast accessibility, efficiency, observability, compatibility, and other distinguishing features (Hanekom & Scriven, 2002).

Methodology

In the current study, the researcher focused on the consumers' perceptions about implementing online marketing strategies in the Business to Business marketing context. To examine this phenomenon, the researcher employed cross-sectional study design and used close-ended structured questionnaires based on 5 points Likert scale to obtain the desired data as survey method helps to avail data from the respondents in a direct, efficient manner (Sana Ali, 2020). Moreover, the researcher used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 64 bit for data analysis purposes. According to (Arkkelin, 2014), Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) offers enormous services to its users. From descriptive statistics to complex multivariate statistical procedures, SPSS provides a complete set of statistical methods.

Population & Sampling:

The population of the current study involves respondents from four major cities of Pakistan, including Islamabad, Lahore, and Karachi. Moreover, the researcher used the "Snowball Sampling" technique for data gathering as snowball sampling helps to gather quantitative data from the sources, which are generally inaccessible (Johnson, 2014). For this purpose, the researcher directly contacted advertising agencies and collect data from their $n= 225$ randomly selected industrial clients. Here using Snowball sampling technique was important as industrial clients are hard to access in Pakistan (Naderifar et al., 2017).

Validity & Reliability of Research Instrument:

The researcher designed a study questionnaire under the supervision of research experts. To further affirm the validity, the researcher also conducted Pearson's Correlation coefficient examination. Likewise, the researcher also scrutinized the reliability of the research instrument by using Intercoder Reliability analysis.

As noted by (Nili et al., 2017), reliability analysis affirms the quality of the research instrument and further authenticates the study results.

Results and Discussion

Statistical Analysis & Results:

Reliability Analysis

Quantitative coding is a substantial part of the research, and today, researchers rely upon on assessing this coding to calculate further the quantitative study results (Nili et al., 2017). To determine the researcher instrument, the researcher employs intercoder reliability to authenticate the generalizability of the research outcomes (Alhumaid et al., 2020). In this regard, the current investigation of the recent study also contains Intercoder Reliability analysis. The Cronbach Alpha Value of .877 affirmed that the research instrument is intensely reliable. **Table 1** below gives an overview of intercoder reliability analysis.

Table 1: Intercoder Reliability Analysis:

Items	Constructs	Cronbach Alpha Value	Status
H1	DC> OA	.806	Reliable
H2	OE>OA	.778	Reliable
H3	ATT> OA	.755	Reliable

Note: DC: Demographical Characteristics, OE: Online Experience, OA: Online Advertising, AT: Adopting New Technologies and Techniques

5.2 Validity of Research Instrument:

Test the validity of the research instrument is an essential aspect of quantitative studies. Validity analysis not only helps to affirm the truth of research instrument it also, describes the extent to which research is capable of bringing authenticated results (Isaac, 2018). The current study also involved validity examination by using Univariate Pearson Correlation Analysis. As seen in **Table 2** below, the research instrument is valid and significant.

Table 2: Univariate Pearson Correlation Coefficient:

OA	DC	O2	AT
.834**			
.000			
.780**	.698**		
.000	.000	.011	
.047	.003	.011	.968
.480	.968	.872	.003

Note: DC: Demographical Characteristics, OE: Online Experience, OA: Online Advertising, AT: Adopting New Technologies and Techniques

Demographical Data of the Study Respondents:

Table 3 below indicates the demographical data of the study respondents. As visible, ($n= 181$ or 80.4%) respondents were males and $n= 44$ or 19.6% were females ($M= 1.20$, $SD= .398$). Moreover, concerning the age of study participants, $n= 82$ or 36.4% were between 31-35 years old, $n= 59$ or 26.2% were 36-40 years old, $n= 32$ or 214.2% of respondents were 18-25 years. Likewise, $n= 25$ or 11.1% of respondents 26-30 years

old, $n= 15$ or 6.7% were between 41-45 years and $n= 12$ or 5.3% of respondents 46 years old or above ($M= 3.16$, $SD= 1.293$). Furthermore, according to the qualification of respondents, $n= 64$ or 28.4% were graduated, $n= 63$ or 28.0% had Bachelor's degree, $n= 53$ or 23.5% of participants were having intermediate certificate, $n= 36$ or 16.0% were matric and only $n= 9$ or 4.0% of respondents were Masters or above ($M= 2.86$, $SD = 1.133$). Thus the total number of respondents was $n= 225$ with the response rate of 100%.

Table 3: Demographical characteristics of the study respondents:

Criterion	Factor	<i>f</i>	%
Gender	Male	181	80.4%
	Female	44	19.6%
	Count	225	
Age	18-25	32	14.2%
	26-30	25	11.1%
	31-35	82	36.4%
	36-40	59	26.2%
	41-45	15	6.7%
	46 or above	12	5.3%
Qualification	Matric	36	16.0%
	Intermediate	53	23.5%
	Bachelors	63	28.0%
	Graduation	64	28.4%
	Masters or above	9	4.0%

According to Habes et al., (2020), online advertising is one of the most effective tools of materializing business purposes. Especially in the Business to a Business marketing context, online advertising is of greater significance (Yoon & Kim, 2016). In this regard, $n= 173$ or 76.8% of respondents agreed that customers could avoid online advertisements for being annoying for them, however, $n= 172$ or 76.4% of participants also agreed that if they have good experience with the online advertising agencies, they might prefer to watch the advertisements. Likewise, $n= 130$ or 57.7% respondents also agreed that online advertising is better than traditional advertising as it is more efficient as they ($n= 112$ or 49.7%) consider it more efficient and digital advertising agencies are more influential ($n= 112$ or 49.7%) and create a more excellent value for the products ($n= 121$ or 53.7%).

Nonetheless, $n= 162$ or 72.0% of participants also agreed that good services from advertising agencies help them to reconsider online advertising in future as it provides numerous benefits ($n= 128$ or 56.8%). Similarly, $n= 141$ or 62.6% of respondents also have good relations with the advertising agencies, and when they avail benefits, they ($n= 128$ or 56.8%) get emotionally involved with the agency employees and services. This emotional involvement also helps $n= 120$ or 53.3% of participants to have positive perceptions about the advertising agencies and consider them ($n= 148$ or 65.7%) as reliable for commercial purposes.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics for Online Advertising in general & Experiences

Factors	M	SD	Variance	Min	Max	N
Predictor Variable: Online Advertising in General						
Avoid advertisements	3.51	1.717	2.947	1	5	225
Good personal experience	3.27	1.091	1.190	1	5	225
Better than the traditional advertisement	3.11	1.433	2.055	1	5	225
Online advertising is more efficient	3.15	1.386	1.920	1	5	225
Online advertising agency is more effective	2.92	1.253	1.570	1	5	225

	Create value for your products				1	5	
		3.01	1.682	2.830			225
Explanatory Experience	Variable:	Online					
	Good response from consumers	3.85	1.727	2.983	1	5	225
	Numerous benefits	3.48	1.296	1.679	1	5	225
	Good client-agency relationship	3.46	1.106	1.223	1	5	225
	Emotionally involved	3.44	1.671	2.792	1	5	225
	Perception of online advertising	3.40	1.509	2.278	1	5	225
	Reliability of online advertising	3.34	1.225	1.501	1	5	225

$N= 165$ or 73.3% of respondents agreed that the quality of service provided by the advertising agency could positively influence their attitude. However, they ($n= 158$ or 67.5%) also ask the advertising agency to keep the clients' personal information as confidential. Similarly, $n= 182$ or 80.8% of respondents also agreed that the level of trust in an agency influences their decisions as keeping your private information under privacy further helps them to prefer using online advertising. According to $n= 180$ or 80.0% of participants, their educational level influences their perception about online advertising and the increased internet usage further affects their ($n= 151$ or 67.1%) decision to use online advertising as well. Moreover, respondents ($n= 41$ or 18.2%) also indicated that using online advertising sometimes becomes expensive for them. However, they ($n= 180$ or 84.0%) still prefer online advertising due to their friendly relations with advertising agencies.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for Personal Characteristics and Online Advertisement:

	Factors	M	SD	Variance	Min	Max	N
Explanatory Characteristics	Variable:	Personal					
	Quality of online advertising	3.43	1.249	1.559	1	5	225
	Issue of privacy	3.32	1.355	1.836	1	5	225
	Trust influences your decision	3.01	1.290	1.665	1	5	225
	Control over your information	2.94	1.759	3.094	1	5	225
	Education levels	3.57	1.721	2.961	1	5	225
	Increased internet penetration	3.56	1.263	1.596	1	5	225
	The decision of using online advertising	3.56	1.034	1.069	1	5	225
	The adoption rate of online advertisement	3.68	1.752	3.068	1	5	225

The growing usage of digital has also influenced the traditional patterns of advertising. Today, online advertising is cost-effective, useful and better than traditional marketing techniques (Akber et al., 2013). To further affirm this, $n= 148$ or 65.7% of participants revealed that they prefer online advertising as it is practical, cost-effective and fast, and ($n= 99$ or 44.0%) also considered that online advertising helps to fulfil their expectations. According to $n= 96$ 42.6% of respondents, their relationship with the agency also influences their decision to prefer online advertising as the more efficiently an agency provides information about recent market trends, the more they ($n= 1433$ or 59.1%) sustain loyal relationships. However, for the $n= 1433$ or 59.1% participants, there are still many gaps between them and advertising agencies, but they ($n= 124$ or 55.1%) still evaluate the possibilities to sustain a good relationship with the online advertising agencies. Therefore, if taken seriously, $n= 139$ or 61.7% of participants also believe that online marketing in general and Business to Business marketing, in particular, have a brighter future in Pakistan.

Table 6: Descriptive Statistics for Adopting New Technology and Techniques

Factors	M	SD	Variance	Min	Max	N
<i>Explanatory Variable: Adopting new technologies</i>						
Cost-saving and convenience	3.37	1.307	1.708	1	5	225
trend and expectation	3.17	1.512	2.287	1	5	225
agency's attitude	3.20	1.474	2.172	1	5	225
Nature of information	3.13	1.626	2.643	1	5	225
Gaps between clients and advertising agencies	3.49	1.547	2.394	1	5	225
evaluation process	3.56	1.407	1.980	1	5	225
The online advertising industry in Pakistan	3.57	1.256	1.577	1	5	225

Hypothesis Testing:

As this study contains three dependent variables, One-way Analysis of Variance and Multiple Regression Analysis were the most practical test to validate the postulations (Grégoire, 2015). In this regard, first, the Analysis of Variance examined the first hypothesis, "**Consumers' perceptions vary based on their demographical characteristics, regarding online advertising in Pakistan**". According to (Patel, 2015), One-Way Analysis of Variance examines the homogeneity of variances among the responses. In simple terms, we use ANOVA to assess equality or non-equality of the means of the gathered data. **Table 7** below provides a brief overview of the One-Way Analysis of Variance. Thus the findings revealed that responses are varying based on their gender, age, and education, and we validate our first hypothesis assuming the clients' varying perceptions regarding online marketing.

Table 7: Test of Homogeneity of Variance

		N	Mean	SD	Levene Statistic	f	Sign
Gender	Male	181	1.20	.398	4.463	.784	.737
	Female	44					
Age	Count	225	2.16	1.293	.961	.765	.760
	25 or below	32					
	26-30	25					
	31-35	82					
	36-40	59					
	41-45	15					
34 or above	12						
Qualification	Matric	36	3.86	1.133	1.008	.283	.999
	Intermediate	53					
	Bachelors	63					
	Graduation	64					
	Masters or above	9					

To examine the first study hypothesis, "Consumers' perceptions vary based on their demographical characteristics, regarding online advertising in Pakistan," the researcher used One-Way Analysis of Variance. As noted by (Patel, 2015), One-Way ANOVA helps analyze the equality of means among the gathered responses. In simple terms, we use ANOVA to examine equality or non-equality of the study population means. One-Way ANOVA is also known as Single Factor Analysis as it explores one independent variable or factor. Moreover, the variable has ordinal or nominal levels (Horn, 2008).

Table 8: Multiple Regression Analysis to Test the Study Hypotheses

H	Relationship	β	<i>t-value</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Direction	Decision
H2	OE>OA	.907	6.358	345.937	.000	Positive	Supported***
H3	ATT> OA	.202	1.502	510.702	.000	Positive	Supported***

Note: DC: Demographical Characteristics, OE: Online Experience, OA: Online Advertising, AT: Adopting New Technologies and Techniques

To further examine the study hypotheses, the researcher employed multiple regression analysis techniques (Alghizzawi et al., 2019). The researchers obtained *t-value*, *RSquare* and *p-value* and mention them in **Table 8** above. Based on data analysis, inferential statistics. Thus there was a strong signification relationship between online advertising, customers' experiences and advanced technology adoption ($\beta = .907$, $P = .000$), ($\beta = .202$, $P = .000$) respectively.

Discussion & Conclduion:

Findings of the current study are consistent with the study of Bala & Verma, (2017) as found that online advertising is transforming and introducing new trends in marketing and business arenas. Advanced communication patterns through social networks enabled to incorporate user preferences into the marketing process and eliminated conventional methods of advertising which was primarily one way and declarative. Interactive mead technology allows mutual communication between marketers and consumers (Uusitalo, 2009). With the ease of access and direct mode of communication, organizations directly communicate with their customers. As improved client-seller communication plays a primary role in successful Business, staying connected with the clients is of greater magnitude—constant contact and feedback help to evaluate the clients' demands and determine what services they expect. Digital media offers the same services and help to sustain successful relations with potential clients (Ohajionu & Mathews, 2015). The current study also indicated the strong impact of demographical characteristics such as age, gender, and education on the perceptions regarding online marketing in Pakistan. These findings are also compatible with the study conducted by (Habes et al., 2021) as they also found demographical factors as influencing factors on digital technology adoption among study participants. Advanced communication resources such as social networking sites are likely to merge user preferences into the advertising process and eliminate traditional perceptions about ads. They are interactive platforms that allow mutual interaction which is symmetrical and persuasive (Gurram et al., 2014). As a result, adoption and integration of digital technology introduced new trends in marketing and Business. Due to its interactive services, the relationship between sellers and buyers are dramatically changed. The online communication provides new space and prospects for especially in terms of Business to Business marketing (Hanekom & Scriven, 2002). Similarly, digital media has also redefined corporate relationships through web-supported alliance as internet advertising is also facilitating the fields of the corporate sector. With its improved ability to share diverse content, advertisers can use several techniques to grab the audience attention (Mam, 2020) quickly. More importantly, digital features such as cookies and IP recognition also help to track and record consumer behaviour that further marketers to

determine the consumers' activities, requirements, and expectations. Thus this fusion of different digital techniques introduced new opportunities to gain in-depth insights (Pomirleanu et al., 2013).

Online Business to Business marketing is offering several opportunities to all the involved parties in Pakistan. Advertising agencies, customers and sellers all are availing improved services, products and generating more significant revenue. Companies prefer online marketing as an integral part of their business policies, generating revenue, and more benefits despite the uttermost importance of traditional media marketing. Online marketing is rapidly flourishing. Online marketers diverse online marketing techniques to help a company avail its goals (Khan & Siddiqui, 2013). Today, online Business to Business marketing is efficient enough to meet all the business requirements. (Raheem, 2013) also discussed the importance of digital marketing in Pakistan as he argued that digital marketing is capable enough to serve all our business objectives. For instance, Rich Overlay Advertisements provide easy access and massive exposure to the online audience, with attractive consumers to grab the customers' attention (Soomro et al., 2012). In this regard, concerning Business to Business Marketing, the goals of both parties are to expand the sales, avail customer loyalty and increase the revenue. For this purpose, online Business to Business marketers adopts different strategies to facilities their customers at maximum (Gu, 2014). Thus with the increased technological development, the Internet allows easy accessibility, exposure, and communication to business companies and marketers. This compatible feature also makes digital marketing better than traditional marketing (Faiz et al., 2019).

Limitations & Recommendations:

This study is limited because the researcher used a finite number of study respondents. Moreover, using snowball sampling further narrow down the scope of the current investigation. Thus, the researcher recommends more studies regarding online marketing, especially in the Business to Business marketing context to further address online marketing extensively.

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